

(MOFs); How, Why, What?!

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Abstract

Metal-Organic Frameworks; MOF) are a new class of nanoporous materials due to their large size pores, high specific surface area, selective absorption of small molecules and optical or magnetic responses in the presence of guest molecules and widely used gas storage. Metallo-organic frameworks are formed by the accumulation of metal ions and clusters as coordination centers and organic ligands as binders. In this paper, metallurgical-organic frameworks are briefly introduced. Then, the design and synthesis of metal-organic frameworks as well as the necessity of using these frameworks, their application in storage and separation of various gases and release of drugs will be studied in detail.

Keywords: Metallo-organic frameworks, coordination, ligand